

Sentinel missions for inland water quantity

Water-ForCE

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List of Acronyms

AHEG	Ad Hoc Expert Group
AMSR-E	Advanced Microwave Scanning Radiometer for EOS
AOLCI	Advanced Ocean and Land Colour Imager
ASCAT	Advanced Scatterometer
ASLSTR	Advanced Sea and Land Surface Temperature Radiometer
CCI	Climate Change Initiative
CCM	Copernicus Contributing Missions
CHIME	Copernicus Hyperspectral Imaging Mission for the Environment
Chl	Chlorophyll
CIMR	Copernicus Imaging Microwave Radiometer
CLMS	Copernicus Land Monitoring Service
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service
CNES	Centre National D'Etudes Spatiales
CO2M	Copernicus Anthropogenic Carbon Dioxide Monitoring
CRISTAL	Copernicus Polar Ice and Snow Topography Altimeter
CSA	Canadian Space Agency
DAHITI	Database for Hydrological Time Series of Inland Waters
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
DLR	German Aerospace Center
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EMODNET	European Marine Observation and Data Networks
ESA	European Space Agency
ET	Evapotranspiration
ERS	EUMETSAT Advanced Retransmission Service
EU	European Union
FLEX	FLuorescence EXplorer

GFM	Global automatic satellite-based flood monitoring
GFZ	German Research Centre for Geosciences
GMES	Global Monitoring for Environment and Security
GRACE	Gravity Recovery and Climate Experiment
GRACE-FO	Gravity Recovery and Climate Experiment Follow-on
GOCE	Gravity Field and Steady-State Ocean Circulation Explorer
HR	High Resolution
HR OC	High-Resolution Ocean
ISRO	Indian Space Research Organisation
KOMPSAT	Korean Multi-purpose Satellites
LR	Low Resolution
LST	Land Surface Temperature
LSTM	Copernicus Land Surface Temperature Monitoring
NG	Next Generation
NGGM	Next Generation of Gravity Missions
MODIS	Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer
MR	Medium Resolution
MSI	Multispectral Instrument
MWIR	Mid Wave Infrared
MWR	Microwave Radiometer
NIR	Near Infrared
OLCI	Ocean and Land Colour Imager
PAN	Panchromatic
ROSE-L	Radar Observing System for Europe at L-band
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SMOS	Soil Moisture and Ocean Salinity
SWE	Snow Water Equivalent
SWOT	Surface Water and Ocean Topography
S1-NG	Sentinel 1 Next Generation
S2-NG	Sentinel 2 Next Generation

S3NG	Sentinel 3 Next Generation
S3 NGO	Sentinel 3 Next Generation Optical
S3NG-T	Sentinel 3 Next Generation Topographic
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
SLSTR	Sea and Land Surface Temperature Radiometer
SPOT	Satellite pour l'Observation de la Terre
SRAL	SAR Radar Altimeter
SWIR	Short Wave Infrared
TIR	Thermal Infrared
TPM	Third Party Missions
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UKSA	United Kingdom Space Agency
USGS	United States Geological Survey
UV	Ultraviolet
VHR	Very High Resolution
VIS	Visible
VNIR	Visible and Near Infrared
WP	Work Package

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Executive summary

This document gives technical recommendations related sensor and platforms features for future Sentinels missions through a crossed analysis between user requirements and existing and planned Sentinel missions in order to make next future Sentinel missions more suitable for inland and coastal water quantity monitoring. The user requirements are collected by several Water-ForCE user consultation activities plus the reviewed bibliography. The main recommendations in such analysis can be summarised as follow: the planned increase of spatial and temporal resolutions of Sentinels NG agrees with the collected high priority demand from the user requirements, water quantity users request a high spatial resolution thermal band for the models and studies which evapotranspiration is a key variable, continuity between missions with inter-band consistency are very important for long time series studies, new gravimetric missions are needed, Sentinel-3NG-T+ ROSE-L will fill the current gap of information in relevant water quantity applications such as river dynamics, monitoring of glaciers and ice caps.

The main goal of this document is to provide inputs for the Water-ForCE Roadmap.

1 Introduction

1.1 Water-ForCE

The **Horizon2020** project [Water-ForCE](#) (Water scenarios For Copernicus Exploitation) will develop a Roadmap for Copernicus **Inland Water Services**, aiming to better integrate the entire inland **water cycle within the [Copernicus Services](#)**. Water-ForCE is analysing possible disconnects between remote sensing / in-situ observation and the user community. Clarity in terms of the needs and expectations of both public and private sectors, as well as the wider research and business innovation opportunities will be delivered. The Roadmap will advise on a strategy to ensure effective uptake of water-related services by end users and further support the implementation of relevant directives and policies.

The Water-ForCE connects experts in water quality and quantity, in policy, research, engineering and service sectors. Through close collaborations with these communities distributed in Working Groups, Water-ForCE is:

- Analysing EU policies to identify where the Copernicus Services can improve monitoring programs and how the Copernicus data can be more effectively used in developing and delivering the next versions of the directives.
- Specifying the requirements for future Copernicus missions (e.g. optical configuration of Sentinel-2E and onward, hyperspectral sensors).
- Optimizing future exploitation for inland water monitoring & research and, consequently, (a) enlarge the service portfolio and (b) improve the performance of current Services.

The project is divided in eight work packages (WP), each of them focusing on a specific problem and/or target of the Copernicus Service (Figure 1). The following report is part of **WP3** which focuses on **Water Quantity**.

Figure 1.- Organizational structure of the different work packages in the Water-ForCE project

1.2 Context WP3

WP3 (Water Quantity) aims to provide insight on the Copernicus products and services supporting water management and modelling. An inventory of water data in existing portfolio offered under Copernicus and other sources has collected, including data on water flux components (flow, evapotranspiration) and water storages (ice, water bodies, soil moisture) and the linkages with groundwater, to ensure an appropriate representation of the hydrological water balance; performing a state-of-the-art assessment and gap analysis. Based on this analysis, the future opportunities for the European Earth Observation program will be evaluated, thereby providing valuable input for the roadmap (WP6).

1.3 Objectives & context T3.5

This report forms the output of the task 3.5 Technical Requirements for future Sentinel sensors to fulfil water quantity monitoring and research requirements. T3.5 evaluates the

technical needs (e.g., revisit time, spatial and spectral resolution) to make future Sentinel missions more suitable for inland water quantity monitoring and for delivering higher level products. The result is a detailed assessment of the optimal long-term mission concept for water.

1.4. Content of the report

This deliverable document is composed by three main parts:

- description of the existing and planned missions.
- suggestions and recommendations collected in Water-ForCE consultation activities.
- discussion/analysis of collected recommendations and conclusions for future Sentinels.

The description of missions consists in the existing Sentinels, plus the complement of the existing contributing missions, and the planned ones: Sentinels expansion and the next generation of Sentinels. This overview gives the global picture of the main data satellite providers to Copernicus services. This review is useful in order to understand which current gaps and suggestions for Sentinels mission improvements are already solved, which ones are near to be solved or still pending.

2.- Copernicus mission overview

Copernicus mission overview:

Sentinel Missions	Sentinel Expansion Missions	Sentinel Next Generation Missions	Copernicus Contributing Missions	
			OPTICAL	SAR
Sentinel 1	CHIME	Sentinel 1 NG	KOMPSTA-2	COSMO-SkyMed
Sentinel 2	CIMR	Sentinel 2NG	KOMPSAT-3	TerraSAR-X
Sentinel 3	CO2M	Sentinel-3	WorldView1,2,3	TanDEM-X
Sentinel 4	CRISTAL	NGOptical	GeoEye-1	RADARSAT-2
Sentinel 5	LSTM	Sentinel-3 NG	Pleiades 1A ,1B	KOMPSAT-5
Sentinel 5p	ROSE-L	Topography	ResourceSat-2	PAZ

Sentinel 6			SPOT 6, 7 SkySat PlanetScope GEOSAT-2 Pleiades Neo Vision-1	ICEYE COSMO-SkyMed Second Generation
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2.1. Sentinels

Copernicus is the European Commission’s Earth Observation Programme, previously known as GMES (Global Monitoring for Environment and Security). The Copernicus space component is responsible for the Sentinels satellites. It includes the procurement, the launch and the operation of the Sentinel satellites, the operation of the ground segment and the distribution of Sentinel’s and contributing missions’ data. The initial goal of the Sentinel programme was to replace the older Earth observation missions which have retired, such as the ERS and Envisat missions. This ensured a continuity of the provision of very valuable remotely sensed information.

Nowadays Sentinel programme is designed to enrich with expansion missions and the new generation versions of the existing ones.

Each mission focuses on a different aspect of Earth observation: atmospheric, oceanic, and land monitoring; all of them provide data for using in many applications on the water domain, and particularly for the water quantity studies, the subject of this deliverable.

Each Sentinel mission is designed to operate in a constellation of two identical satellites to fulfill the revisit and the coverage requirements for each mission, providing robust datasets for all Copernicus services. The first two satellites (A and B) for each mission are launched as soon as possible whereas the two follow-on satellites (C and D) are prepared to be launched by the end of the scheduled mission.

Each mission carries a different technology, such as radar and multi-spectral imaging instruments for land, ocean and atmospheric monitoring:

Sentinel 1:

Sentinel 1 is a mission at 693 km altitude of sun-synchronous near polar orbit with **C-SAR**, Synthetic Aperture Radar instrument at 5.405 GHz at different spatial resolutions: 4-100 m and swath range 80 km to 400 km. 3-day revisit at equator (~2 days in Europe, ~daily in high latitudes) (Rostan et al. 2011). The mission is composed of a constellation of two satellites, currently, Sentinel-1A was launched on 3 April 2014 and Sentinel-1B on 25 April 2016 (detected major anomaly on 23 December 2021, ended 3 August 2022). Considering that Sentinel-1B ended on 3 August 2022, this force the plans to launch Sentinel-1C as soon as possible. Sentinel-1C scheduled for launch in the second half of April 2023 (Potin et al., 2022). Furthermore, to ensure a continuity of data, the European Commission anticipated Sentinel-1D launch, that is expected to take place in the second half of 2024 (ESA, 2022). Their mission is the continuity of SAR imagery by ERS-1 and ERS-2.

They provide very valuable data for the monitoring of sea and land ice, surveillance of oil spills and ships, monitoring of marine wind and waves, monitoring of land surface motion risks, and the mapping of forest, water, and soil management.

Sentinel 2:

Sentinel-2 is a mission at 786 km altitude of sun-synchronous near polar orbit with Multispectral Instrument (MSI) at different spatial resolutions: 10, 20, 60 m, swath width of 290 km. 5-days revisit at equator, 2-3 days at mid latitudes. The MSI is composed by 13 spectral bands range from the Visible (VIS) and Near Infra-Red (NIR) to the Short Wave Infra-Red (SWIR) (see Fig 2). They provide continuity for the SPOT and Landsat missions. The mission is composed by a constellation of 2 satellites, currently, Sentinel-2A was launched on 23 June 2015 and Sentinel-2B followed on 7 March 2017. Sentinel-2C is scheduled for mid 2024 ([ESA](#), 2022), and Sentinel-2D for 2025 (Gascon et al., 2022)

They are used for monitoring vegetation in agriculture and forest, for inland and coastal water quality, for source of information in land cover mapping and many other applications. (Spoto et al 2012)

Figure 2.- Spatial resolution of Sentinel-2 spectral bands; image credit: ESA

Sentinel 3:

Sentinel-3 is a mission at 815 km altitude in a sun-synchronous polar orbit. They have three instruments on board: the Ocean and Land Colour Imager (**OLCI**); another imaging radiometer, the Sea and Land Surface Temperature Radiometer (**SLSTR**); and a radar altimeter (**SRAL**) which is complemented by a Microwave Radiometer (MWR) (Strømme & Wilson, 2022). OLCI has 21 spectral bands ranging over VNIR (visual and near-infrared) and SWIR (short-wave infrared), with a spatial resolution of 300m and a swath of 1270 km. The key mission of the Sentinel-3 OLCI instrument is the continuity of the Envisat MERIS. SLSTR has 11 spectral bands: the VNIR and SWIR channels have three bands each with a resolution of 500 m, and the MWIR (medium wave infrared) and TIR (thermal infrared) channels cover five bands with a spatial resolution of 1 km. The SRAL altimeters on Sentinel-3A and -3B are the first to operate in delay-Doppler or SAR mode over all Earth surfaces, which enables better spatial resolution of the signal in the along-track direction and improved noise reduction through multi-looking, whilst the radiometer is a two-channel nadir-viewing system. SRAL operates in both C-band and Ku-band with a resolution of 300 m, while MWR operates in both K-band and Ka-band. The MWR revisit time is four days at equator (less in higher latitudes). (Seitz et al 2010). The mission is composed by a constellation of 2 satellites flying on the same orbital plane separated 140° (Strømme & Wilson, 2022), currently, Sentinel-3A was launched on 16 February 2016 and Sentinel-3B followed on April 2018.

Launch of Sentinel-3C is envisaged for 2024-2025 (ESA, 2022) and Sentinel-3D is planned by 2025 (<https://www.eumetsat.int/our-satellites/sentinel-series?sjid=future>)

Sentinel-3 allows to measure systematically Earth's oceans, land, ice and atmosphere monitoring and to understand large-scale global dynamics, also it provides essential information in near-real time for ocean and weather forecasting. In particular SRAL is used to derive water level height of both ocean and inland water surfaces (rivers and/or reservoirs) and ice thickness.

Sentinel 4:

The Sentinel-4 instruments will be carried on Meteosat Third Generation satellites. The Sentinel-4 mission is made up of the Ultraviolet Visible Near-infrared (UVN) spectrometer and data from the Infrared Sounder (IRS). They will monitor air quality, trace gases and aerosols over Europe hourly at 8 km spatial resolution (<https://www.eumetsat.int/sentinel-4>). S4 together with the US Tropospheric Emissions: Monitoring of Pollution (TEMPO) and the South Korean Geostationary Environment Monitoring Spectrometer (GEMS), form a constellation of geostationary instruments that will provide Air quality data over a large part of the northern hemisphere (https://www.esa.int/Applications/Observing_the_Earth/Copernicus/Sentinel-4-set_to_join_next_weather_satellite) The scheduled launch is on early 2024 (<https://www.eumetsat.int/our-satellites/sentinel-series?sjid=future>).

Sentinel 5:

Sentinel-5 consist of spectrometer instrument (UV, VIS, NIR, SWIR) for atmospheric measurements on air quality, climate forcing, ozone and UV radiation with a swath width of 2.670km and a spatial resolution of 50 x50 km(UV1) and 7,5 x 7,5 km (other channels)(<https://sentinels.copernicus.eu/web/sentinel/missions/sentinel-5>). The instrument will be embarked as a Customer Furnished Item (CFI) on the MetOP-SG A1 satellite scheduled to launch at early 2024 (<https://www.eumetsat.int/our-satellites/sentinel-series>).

Sentinel 5 Precursor:

Sentinel-5P is a mission at 820 km altitude in a near-polar, sun-synchronous, to provide atmospheric composition and air quality TROPospheric Monitoring Instrument (TROPOMI) at 5.5 x 3.5 km of spatial resolution and daily global coverage. TROPOMI is a passive grating imaging spectrometer that has a swath width of 2600 km. It includes four spectrometers split into two bands: 2 in Ultraviolet (UV), 2 in VIS, 2 in NIR and 2 in SWIR.

Sentinel-5p was taken into orbit on 13 October 2017, to reduce the gap in global atmospheric data products available between SCIMACHY instrument of Envisat ESA satellite (ended in April 2021), NASA'S OMI/AURA and the future Copernicus Sentinel-4 and Sentinel-5 missions.

The satellite position was carefully chosen to facilitate the data synergy with NASA's Suomi-NPP VIIRS(Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite) high resolution cloud mask to process TROPOMI methane product

<https://sentinels.copernicus.eu/web/sentinel/missions/sentinel-5p>,

Sentinel 6:

Sentinel-6, known as Sentinel-6 Michael Freilich, is a mission at 1336 km altitude, on a non sun-synchronous orbit, with a repeat cycle of 9.92 days, to extend the legacy of sea-surface height measurements until at least 2030 (Donlon et al., 2021). Sentinel- 6, main payload is Poseidon-4, a dual frequency (C/Ku-band) nadir-pointing radar altimeter. The innovative interleaved mode, allows to process radar data in two parallel chains: one as a synthetic aperture radar (SAR) processing Ku-band providing high precision altimeter measurements, and a second that provides a low Resolution Mode compatible with historical altimetry data (Donlon et al., 2021). The mission includes two satellites that will fly sequentially with an expected launch separation of 5 years into the altimetry reference orbit with S6-MF overlapping with Jason-3: Sentinel-6A was taken into orbit on 21 Nov 2020, and Sentinel 6B is planned for 2025.

Sentinel-6 is an Earth Observation satellite mission developed to provide enhanced continuity to the very stable time series of mean sea level measurements and ocean sea state that started in 1992, with the TOPEX/Poseidon mission, and then continued by the Jason-1, Jason-2 and Jason-3 satellite missions. Since 1992 four satellite radar altimeter missions have provided a sustained 'reference' altimetry capability occupying the same 'reference' orbit ($\pm 66.04^\circ$ inclination, 1339-1356 km altitude, 112 min per revolution) providing

a 9.9-day repeat track orbit. In addition to sea surface height and its oceanographic application, Sentinel 6 also provides valuable measurements on land water, such as monitoring variations on high and extent of rivers, lakes, reservoirs and flooded regions (Donlon et al., 2021).

Figure 3.- Schedule of Sentinels missions.

Source: <https://twitter.com/copernicuseu/status/642308403612753920>

2.2 Sentinel Expansion missions

Sentinel expansion aims to provide new observations to match the emerging user needs, climate change (causes and effects), the arctic, sustainable land use and agriculture and food security. There are six high priority candidate 'expansion' mission that will eventually become Sentinel-7 to Sentinel-12 missions:

CHIME: Copernicus Hyperspectral Imaging Mission for the Environment will provide observations for the sustainable use of natural resources, i.e. agriculture nutrients, water, soil properties, biodiversity indicators, etc.

The user requirements for the mission are a global coverage with a revisit time of 10-12.5 days, a spatial resolution of 20-30m, continuous spectral coverage between 400 and 2500nm. Minimum Signal-to-Noise ratio have been required for an improved water observation. It has also been requested that the platform allows the inter-operability with other missions including Sentinel-2, Sentinel-3, FLEX; EnMAP, PRISMA, SHALOM, and EMIT. Synergies with other missions, like Sentinel-2, would help fulfil high temporal and spatial resolution (through spatial sharpening of hyperspectral imagery with sentinel-2) requirement form field like agriculture or in-land waters (Earth and Mission Science Division, 2019; European Commission, 2019; Taramelli et al., 2020).

CIMR: Copernicus Imaging Microwave Radiometer satellites will contain conically scanning microwave radiometer imagers at five spectral bands, corresponding to frequencies of 1.4, 6.9, 10.65, 18.7, and 36.5 GHz.

There are three main parameters which will be sought by CIMR, the Sea Surface Temperature (SST), the Sea-Surface Salinity (SSS) and a wide variety of floating sea ice parameters, in particular Sea Ice Concentration (SIC). It will be able to provide as well as sea ice thickness, wind speed, snow water equivalent and soil moisture and it will support of ship navigation. CIMR mission will provide a spatial resolution of ~ 5km and sub-daily temporal resolution. This is a High-Priority Copernicus Mission to support EU policy for the Artic (Earth and Mission Science Division, 2020b).

CO2M: Copernicus Anthropogenic Carbon Dioxide Monitoring will allow to monitor the anthropogenic CO₂ emissions at country/regional and megacities scale using a NIR and SWI spectrometer. This is a priority mission, to assess the effectiveness of the Paris Climate Agreement on CO₂ reduction commitments (Earth and Mission Science Division, 2020a).

CRISTAL: Copernicus Polar Ice and Snow Topography Altimeter will carry a dual-frequency synthetic-aperture radar altimeter as its primary payload for measuring surface height and a passive microwave radiometer to support atmospheric corrections and surface-type

classification. The altimeter will have interferometric capabilities at Ku-band for improved ground resolution and a second (non-interferometric) Ka-band frequency to provide information on snow layer properties.

It will provide land ice elevation, sea ice thickness, permafrost and snow loading in support to coastal and inland waters applications and climate change applications as well (Kern et al., 2020).

LSTM: Copernicus Land Surface Temperature Monitoring mission will provide observations with a high spatio-temporal resolution in the thermal infrared (TIR). These measurements complement the existing family of Copernicus satellites for observing the land and coastal areas. In particular, there will be direct synergies with the Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-3 missions, considering that Sentinel-1 provides radar imagery, Sentinel-2 high resolution optical, Sentinel-3 optical, thermal and altimetry data. The primary objective of the LSTM mission is to enable timely and accurate monitoring of evapotranspiration at a finer scale than Sentinel-3. ET is a key variable for agriculture applications on the term of water management. Monitoring of high resolution (field scale) allows the assessment of crop water status, and the optimisation of water resources through irrigation management schemes. ESA's project Sen-ET developed a methodology for estimating ET downscaling Sentinel 3 thermal data using Sentinel 2 imagery to fill the lack of thermal data with a high spatio-temporal resolution required modelling ET at field-scale until mission like LSTM are on orbit (Guzinski et al., 2020). The mission requirements are set at a resolution between 30 to 50 m and a daily to 3 days revisit time (Koetz et al., 2021)

ROSE-L: Radar Observing System for Europe on L-band mission responds to the Land Monitoring and Emergency Management services requirements. It will provide measurements of forest cover, snow and ice, temporal variations in soil moisture and crop type, ground movement and deformation. It will improve disaster mitigation, earthquakes and volcanoes, landslides, flooding etc. This L-band SAR mission will complement existing and future C-band SAR missions to create the Radar Observing System for Europe (ROSE). The high penetration of L-band wavelength through natural material like vegetation, dry snow and ice, will complement Sentinel-1 observations to constitute a multi-band space-born SAR system, providing enhanced mapping capabilities. It has been required that the

mission offers a 6 days global coverage cycle with quad-polarimetric acquisitions at a spatial resolution higher than 50m² (e.g., 5x10m or similar) (Davidson et al., 2019)

2.3 Sentinel Next Generation missions

ESA initiated in 2018 an architectural design study to prepare the development of the next generation of the Sentinel 1 (S1), Sentinel 2 (S2) and Sentinel 3 (S3). The aim of this activity was to analyse and trade-off different architectural options for the Next-Generation (NG) of the Copernicus Space Component missions in the 2032 time horizon. Currently the mission requirements for Sentinel-1 NG, Sentinel-2 NG and Sentinel-3 NG have been defined and the potential sensors configurations are under analysis.

Sentinel-1 Next Generation (S1-NG):

Main Mission's goal is to ensure C-Band data continuity beyond the next decade (2030). S1-NG mission will fulfil three requirements: (1) to ensure continuity of services and applications relying on Sentinel-1, (2) Enhanced existing services and applications, and (3) enable new applications improving performance and addressing observation gaps. The mission will include key enhanced capabilities such as a spatial resolution of 5x5m (20x5m for S1), a wider swath of more than 400km (250 IW-400 EW for S1), quad-polarimetric capabilities and more frequent revisit capability and a lower NESZ of -26db (-22db for S1). Sentinel-1NG is not envisaged as an isolated mission, but as part of a system working in synergy with the current Sentinel 1 and future ROSE-L to cover the same ground area a few seconds apart. S1-NG is expected to be launched in 2032 (Lodadio, 2022).

Sentinel-2 Next Generation (S2-NG)

S2-NG, scheduled for launch in early 2030s, aims to become the wide-swath, moderate to high-resolution, multispectral imaging mission of reference in Europe. The main mission's goals are to ensure continuity of services to the current Sentinel-2 applications, and to provide enhanced capabilities with the implementation of a new generation sensor, the Advanced Multi-spectral Imager (AMSI).

The new sensor will allow higher spatial resolution (goal of 5x5m for VIS/NIR). Will also include additional bands, besides the 12 heritage bands from S2, to enable new applications fulfilling specific needs expressed by the user community. The mission has targeted a lower revisit time, following users requests. User requirements of VHR or panchromatic (PAN) band with a 2.5m resolution will not be addressed in S2-NG mission, but is under evaluation the implementation through an hybrid constellation. S2-NG will be complementary to other Copernicus missions (CHIME, LSTM, Sentinel-3NG) and highly coordinated with future NASA/USGS Landsat Next (Celesti et al., 2022).

Sentinel-3 Next Generation:

The next generation of Sentinel-3 space components that will ensure continuity to the Copernicus services are foreseen to be launched in the 2032, For optimized sampling, S3-NG splits in two components: (1) the optical component (S3 NG OPT) and (2) the topographic component (S3NG-T) (Donlon et al., 2022)

Sentinel-3 Next Generation Optical Mission:

Following on the S3, S3 NGO will guarantee the continuity of the data feed to Copernicus applications and services and evolve into enhanced capabilities. S3 NGO is envisaged as a 2-satellite constellation to cover the 2 days (with a goal of 1 day) revisit time and spatial resolution requirements of the mission. The payload will consist on two sensor the Advanced Ocean and Land Colour Imager (AOLCI) and the Advanced Sea and Land Surface Temperature Radiometer (ASLSTR) replacing S3 OLCI and SLSTR. The key requirements for AOLCI are an improved spatial resolution at nadir of at least 150m (with a goal of 100m) for coastal and inland observations, and a larger number of spectral bands than his precursor S3 OLCI and a goal of a full on-board recorded spectrum. In particular, new 12400 and 16100 nm in the SWIR identified as crucial by the AHEG (Ad Hoc Expert Group). The desired targets for the new ASLSTR, following user's requirements, are an improved spatial resolution of at least 500m and additional spectral bands in the MWIR (3900, 4090, 8700 nm) and VIS (440nm).

Additional hyperspectral needs and thermal observations at an improved spatial resolution will be covered by CHIME and LSTM Expansion missions (Cipollini, 2022, LPS)

Sentinel-3 Next Generation Topography (S3NG-T):

The primary objectives of S3NG-T are to ensure the continuity of S3, extending the time series of nadir altimeter measurements, and to provide enhanced capabilities following evolving user requirements. S3NG-T will offer improved sampling coverage and revisit times to $\leq 50\text{km}$ and ≤ 5 days respectively, and improved performance. Hydrology has been elevated to a Primary Objective by EC for S3NG-T, and all mentioned improved features will be important to obtain Hydrology Water Surface Elevation measurements.

Enhanced sampling and coverage requirements must be achieved through a constellation of spacecraft flying in a sun-synchronous orbit. The different constellation scenarios under study are: (1) A set of 10-12 nadir Ka-band altimeters with integrated radiometers, (2) 2 satellites with a swath Ka-band altimeter and nadir Ku-Band altimeter or, (3) a hybrid constellation including both swath altimeter and nadir pointing satellites. All possible scenarios take Sentinel-6/NG as its reference mission to provide common reference measurements for S3NG-T (Donlon et al., 2022, Cipollini, 2022).

2.4 Copernicus Contributing missions

In addition to data provided by the Sentinel satellites, Copernicus Contributing Missions (CCM) fill the gaps of HR and VHR systematic coverage and on-demand, needed for environmental and climate policy development. Contributing missions include optical and SAR missions from ESA, their Member States, Eumetsat, commercial VHR and other European and international third-party mission operators that make some of their data available for Copernicus. They play a crucial role, delivering complementary data at VHR, HR and MR to satisfy whole range of observational requirements. CCM contribute to one or more of the systematic optical and SAR collection at VHR, HR, and MRHR (some of which are cloud-free) covering 39 European countries. All registered users have view access to the systematic dataset collection. But only those users registered under Public authorities, Copernicus Services, Space research (EU funded), Non-space research (EU funded), EU institutions or International organisations categories will have download access to some of the collections.

Only users registered under Copernicus Services or EU-funded space research projects categories can place an order in the on-demand datasets with a set quota. On-demand datasets can be ordered on a Standard (task scheduled from 2 days in advance) or Rush (task scheduled between 16 and 48 h in advance) tasking lead time. Imagery can be requested in different resolution categories:

- VHR1: Very High Resolution 1, where resolution: $\leq 1\text{m}$
- VHR2: Very High Resolution 2, where resolution: $>1\text{m}$ and $\leq 4\text{m}$
- HR1: High Resolution 1, where resolution: $>4\text{m}$ and $\leq 10\text{m}$
- HR2: High Resolution 2, where resolution: $>10\text{m}$ and $\leq 30\text{m}$
- MR1: Medium Resolution, where resolution: $>30\text{m}$ and $\leq 100\text{m}$

CCM Optical missions:

KOMPSAT-2 and KOMPSAT-3 (Korean Multipurpose Satellites): Part of the Arirang fleet of multipurpose satellites, are owned by the Korean government and operated by Korean Aerospace Research Institute (KAR). Payload is a Multispectral (PAN, VNIR) camera that captures VHR panchromatic and multispectral imagery. The satellites are used in applications such as land planning, agriculture and civil engineering. KOMPSAT-2 and 3 missions contribute in systematic (only KOMPSAT-3) and on-demand CCM dataset: Standard Optical VHR1, and VHR2.

WorldView-1,-2 and -3: Part of the WorldView series operated by the US Company Maxar. World Wide-1 and 2 carry a High-capacity, panchromatic imaging system capable of offering 1 million km^2 at 0,5m resolution per day. WorldView-3 carries a multi-payload providing PAN(0.31m), VNIR (1.24m), SWIR(3.7m) (<https://resources.maxar.com/data-sheets/worldview-3>). Worldview mission contributes to systematic (only WorldView-2 and -3) on-demand CCM datasets: Standard and Rush Optical VHR1.

GeoEye-1: Part of the WorldView series operated by the US Company Maxar, Carries a Multispectral imager (PAN, VNIR) with a pan-sharpened resolution of 0.5m suited for large-

scale mapping projects. GeoEye-1 mission contributes to systematic and on-demand CCM datasets: Standard and Rush Optical VHR1, VHR2

Pléiades 1A and Pléiades 1B: the French Pléiades constellation consists of two satellites providing very high-resolution images of the Earth with a daily revisit capacity. The mission is designed for cartography, agriculture, forestry, hydrology and geological applications. The Pléiades mission contributes to systematic and on-demand CCM datasets: Standard and Rush Optical VHR1, VHR2.

ResourceSat-2: also known as IRS-R2, is an Indian Space Research Organisation (ISRO), launched in 2011. IRS-R2 carries two Multispectral sensors (VIS/NIR/SWIR) 5,8 and 23,5m resolution (https://www.euromap.de/docs/doc_007.html). It is designed for land and water resource management. ResourceSat contributes to some systematic data sets in Optical VHR, HR and MR1.

SPOT 6 and SPOT 7 (Satellite Pour l'Observation de la Terre): Twin commercial Earth observation satellites operated by Airbus Defence and Space. They carry a PAN and Multispectral sensors (VIS/NIR/PAN) capturing large areas at a 1.5m resolution with a daily revisit time (<https://www.intelligence-airbusds.com/imagery/constellation/spot/>, <https://www.eoportal.org/satellite-missions/spot-6-7#mission-capabilities>), in a mission suited for mapping, agriculture and land management applications. SPOT 6 and 7 missions contribute to systematic and on-demand CCM datasets: Standard Optical and Rush VHR1, and VHR2.

SkySat: Is a constellation of 21 high-resolution earth imaging satellites owned by the commercial company Planet Labs. Equipped with optical images with PAN/VIS/NIR band achieve a PAN resolution of 0.9 and a multispectral of 2m. SKYSat imagery is commercially marketed for a wide variety of applications such as monitoring, land use planning, environmental assessment, resources management, tourism, mapping and scientific use (<https://www.eoportal.org/satellite-missions/skysat#test-sites>). SkySat contributes to on-demand CCM dataset: Rush Optical VHR1.

PlanetScope: Satellite constellation of approximately 130 CubeSats, satellites owned by the commercial company Planet Labs. Equipped with a multispectral sensor capturing imagery constantly at a resolution of 3.7m (nadir) with a daily revisit time (<https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/documents/20142/37627/Planet-combined-imagery-product-specs-2020.pdf>). Planet Scope contributes to the on-demand CCM datasets: Optical Standard and Rush VHR2.

GEOSAT-2: is a very-high resolution multispectral satellite, owned by the private company GEOSAT. Carries an Optical sensor delivering sub-metric multispectral (PAN/VNIR) imagery over large areas and an average 2-days revisit time (<https://geosat.space/>). GEOSAT-2 contributes in systematic and on-demand CCM datasets: Standard and Rush Optical VHR1 and VHR2.

Pleiades Neo is a constellation of four identical VHR optical satellites operated by Airbus. The first two mission's satellites were launched on April and August 2021. The third and fourth satellites of the constellation were lost during an unsuccessful launch on December 2022. Pleiades Neo payload consist of a panchromatic multispectral sensor (Deep Blue, VIS, NIR, PAN) with a sub-meter resolution (30cm) and a revisit capacity of twice daily, anywhere in the world (<https://www.eoportal.org/satellite-missions/pleiades-neo#overview>, <https://www.intelligence-airbusds.com>, <https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/missions/pleiades-neo>). Pleiades Neo contributes to the on-demand CCM datasets: Standard and Rush VHR1 and VHR2.

Vision- 1 is a high-resolution satellite managed by Airbus Defense and Space, capturing sub-meter resolution imagery (VNIR) (<https://www.intelligence-airbusds.com/imagery/constellation/vision1/>).

CCM SAR missions:

COSMO-SkyMed: the Constellation of small Satellites for the Mediterranean basin Observation, was an ASI (Agenzia Spaziale Italiana) and the Italian Ministry of Defense Earth

observation satellite system that consists of (in the 1st generation) four satellites equipped with high resolution Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) sensors operating in the X-band. The mission's applications are seismic hazard analysis, environmental disaster monitoring and agricultural mapping. COSMO-SkyMed contributes to systematic and on-demand CCM datasets: SAR Standard and Rush at VHR1, VHR2, HR1, HR2, and MR1.

TerraSAR-X and TanDEM-X: result from a partnership between the German Aerospace Center (DLR) and Airbus DS Goe GmbH, they are identical Earth Observation satellite carrying a high frequency X-Band SAR sensor. TerraSAR-X was launched in June 2007 and TanDEM-X in June 2010. Both satellites fly in a close formation with a cross-track distance of 300-500 m allowing a single-pass SAR Interferometer configuration that provides a unmatched geometric accuracy. The VHR and wide area coverage makes it particularly suited to a wide range of applications (e.g. land use / land cover mapping, topographic mapping, forest monitoring, emergency response monitoring, maritime applications and environmental monitoring). TerraSAR-X contributes to systematic and on-demand CCM datasets: SAR Standard and Rush at VHR1, VHR2, HR1, HR2, and MR1. TanDEM-X contributes to SAR High Resolution 2-Medium Resolution 1 sea ice monitoring 2011-2014 (DWH_MG1_CORE_11) dataset.

RADARSAT-2: Result of a partnership between MDA and the Canadian Space Agency (CSA), launched in 2007. The mission carries a sensor operating in the C-band, providing 3m HR imaging used in applications for environmental monitoring, resource management and coastal surveillance. RADARSAT-2 contributes to systematic and on-demand CCM datasets SAR Standard and Rush at VHR2, HR1, HR2, and MR1

KOMPSAT-5 (Korean Multi-purpose Satellite 5, also referred as Arirang-5): Part of the Arirang fleet, it is owned by the Korean government and operated by the Korean Aerospace Research Institute (KARI). KOMPSAT-6, currently under development, will be the successor of KOMPSAT-5, aims to be launched In 2024 (KARI, 2021). Carries a X-band SAR that provides imagery at 20, 2.5, 1 and 0.85 m resolution. KOMPTSAT-5 contributes to on-demand CCM datasets: SAR standard VHR1 and VHR2.

PAZ: X-band SAR satellite, the result of the partnership between Hisdesat and Airbus Defence and Space. PAZ deliver 100 images daily at 0.25m resolution. It has a revisit time of 11 days, but can access any location on earth every 24h. PAZ contributes to systematic and on-demand CCM dataset: SAR Standard and Rush at VHR1, VHR2, HR1, HR2, and MR1

ICEYE: A constellation of small X-band SAR satellites, operated by YCEYE company. The constellation offers global coverage at a sub-meter resolution with the capacity to revisit an area of interest multiple times every 24hallowing multiple land and sea monitoring applications (<https://www.iceye.com>). ICEYE contributes to on-demand CCM dataset: SAR Standard and Rush at VHR1, VHR2, HR1

Upcoming CCM :

COSMO-SkyMed second generation: CSG is a constellation of 4 satellites (2 of them already launched in December 2019 and January 2022, the other two scheduled for launch in 2024 and 2025) developed by the Agenzia Spaziale Italiana (ASI) and funded by the Italian Ministry of Defense. The mission carries a X-band SAR with improved resolution capabilities and provides continuity to COSMO-SkyMed (<https://www.eoportal.org/satellite-missions/cosmo-skymed-second-generation#summary>)

Figure 4.-: Classification of contributing missions.

Source: https://spacedata.copernicus.eu/web/guest/contributing_missions

3.- Other Earth Observation missions

Other relevant Earth Observation Missions overview:

ESA Earth Explorers	ESA Earth Watch	Third Party Missions		
		OPTICAL	SAR	Others
SMOS RyoSat-2 FLEX BIOMASS	PROBA-V	GeoEye-1 GEOSAT-2 KOMPSAT-2 PlanetScope Pleiades 1A ,1B ResourceSat-2 SkySat SPOT 6, 7 Vision 1 WorldView 1,2,3,4 Ikonos-2 QuickBird ALOS-1 DMC RadipEye	COSMO- SkyMed ICEYE PAZ RADARSAT 2 TerraSAR-X TanDEM-X	GRACE GRACE-FO

3.1 ESA Earth Explorers

ESA’s Earth Explorers are smaller research missions dedicated to specific aspects of our Earth’s environment. Earth Explorer missions focus on research of the atmosphere, biosphere, hydrosphere, cryosphere and the Earth’s interior with the overall emphasis on learning more about the interactions between these components and the impact that human activity has on natural Earth processes. SMOS and CryoSat-2 contribute to Copernicus and the future FLEX will also contribute.

SMOS (Soil Moisture and Ocean Salinity), was launched on 2 November 2009. SMOS carries a Microwave Imaging Radiometer with Aperture Synthesis (MIRAS), a passive microwave 2-D interferometric polarimetric radiometer (L-Band, 1.4 GHz, 21 cm). Thanks to SMOS, numerous applications have been exploited over unfrozen land surface, i.e. using a range of derived surface soil moisture and vegetation products. Soil moisture information has been used for drought monitoring and agricultural purposes. SMOS data have also been assimilated into land surface models and used for numerical weather prediction to estimate unobserved variables, such as root zone soil moisture; groundwater in peatlands; to constrain C-cycle and evapotranspiration models; for irrigation estimations; for river discharge predictions and hazards prevention, such as landslides and fires. Since the SMOS launch, several variables related to the cryosphere have been studied: sea ice thickness, frozen soil, continental ice sheets temperature, and snow liquid water content. L-band allows monitoring of thin sea ice (< 1 m) (<https://earth.esa.int>).

CryoSat-2, launched on 8 April 2010, is the first ESA mission dedicated to studying Earth's cryosphere, providing thickness measurement of the Earth's continental ice sheets and marine ice cover. CryoSat uses a unique radar instrument called SIRAL (Synthetic Aperture Interferometric Radar Altimeter), specifically designed to measure sea ice and polar ice sheets, particularly at their edges where icebergs calve. CryoSat orbits at an unusually high inclination, reaching latitudes of 88° North and South. (<https://earth.esa.int>).

FLEX: The FLuorescence EXplorer (FLEX) mission will provide global maps of vegetation fluorescence that can reflect photosynthetic activity and plant health and stress. In turn, this is not only important for a better understanding of the global carbon cycle, but also for agricultural management and food security. This is of particular relevance due to demand the growing world population is placing on the production of food. Currently it is not possible to measure photosynthetic activity from space, but FLEX's novel instrument will be capable of achieving this. FLEX will fly in tandem with the Copernicus Sentinel-3 mission, in particular working in combination with the OLCI and SLSTR instruments Sentinel-3 carries. FLEX is expected to be launched in 2025, with a three and a half year design lifetime (<https://earth.esa.int>).

BIOMASS: BIOMASS is the 7th Earth Explorer mission, selected for development In May 2023. BIOMASS will carry the first spaceborne P-band SAR. The mission's objective is to measure the global distribution of forest biomass by reducing the uncertainty in calculating carbon stock and fluxes associated with the terrestrial biosphere. The large wavelength (~70cm) will provide enough penetration into the forest layers to evaluate biomass. Furthermore, P-Band observation can offer a wide range of applications, such as mapping subsurface geological features in forests, deserts and ice sheets. In the context of "water quantity", the measurements made by BIOMASS allow estimating glacier and ice-sheet velocities, a variable critical to understand Ice-sheet mass loss in the frame of Climate Change. BIOMASS launch is expected around April 2024. (<https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/missions/biomass>, https://www.esa.int/Applications/Observing_the_Earth/FutureEO/Biomass, <https://www.eoportal.org/satellite-missions/biomass#biomass-biomass-monitoring-mission-for-carbon-assessment>)

3.2 ESA Earth Watch

Earth Watch program consist of missions developed and operated in partnership with other organisations.

PROBA-V: Project for On-Board Autonomy with instrument is the Compact High Resolution Imaging Spectrometer (CHRIS), which has applications in atmosphere, land, agriculture and oceans and coast.

3.3 ESA Third Party Missions (TPM):

ESA's TPM arrangement has been operating for over 45 years, establishing agreements between ESA and non-ESA EO missions around the world, to promote the availability of their data products freely for research and pre-operational applications developments.

Depending on the mission, users with an Earth Online login profile can access the TPM data sets through:

- a) Immediate download from the TPM Online Dissemination Services platform;
- b) a Fast Approval request, where ESA will review and approve the data download;
- c) a Project Proposal, where ESA and the TPM data provider will review the application to grant approval; or
- d) users will be redirected to the TPM website data portal to request the download, usually after registration (Spazio, 2022).

Figure 5.- Summary of ESA Third Party Missions archive collection at date 22 July 2022. Source: <https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/news/interactive-summary-of-esa-third-party-mission-collections>

Figure 6.- Timeline showing instruments and temporal coverage of TPM (Spazio, 2022)

In general, missions under a CCM agreement, also have data distribution agreements with ESA as a TPM. Relevant TPM that are also CCM, are described in section 2.4 "Copernicus Contributing Missions". This is the case of:

- OPTICAL: GeoEye-1, GEOSAT-2, KOMPSAT-2, PlanetScope, Pleiades 1A/1B, ResourceSat-2, SkySat, SPOT 6/7, Vision 1 and WorldView 1/2/3.

- SAR: COSMO-SkyMed, ICEYE, PAZ, RADARSAT-2, TerraSAR-X and TanDEM-X.

Other TPM relevant to the present topic are:

DMC: the Disaster Monitoring Constellation (DMC) is a UK constellation of remote-sensing satellites. There have been eight satellites in the DMC-program; three are currently (as of 2020) active. The constellation provides emergency Earth imaging for disaster relief under the International Charter for Space and Major Disasters.

GRACE & GRACE-FO: Gravity Recovery and Climate Experiment, is a gravity study mission, a joint project between NASA and DLR. The mission consisted on two identical satellites GRACE-A and GRACE -B located in the same orbit 220km apart, The mission was launched on March 2002 and ended on October 2017. During its operational time, GRACE allowed to observe water mass movements, in solid, liquid or vapor state; in between Earth's atmosphere, oceans, land, ice sheets and underground, by tracking changes on Earth's gravitational pull. GRACE Follow-On (GRACE-FO), continuity mission,, was launched on May 2018. The mission is a partnership between NASA and GFZ. (<https://gracefo.jpl.nasa.gov>)

RapidEye: Was a constellation of five identical satellites owned and operated by Planet, launched on August 2008 and deactivated on March 2020. Each satellite carried a identical multispectral Imager sensor (VIS/NIR) called RapidEye Earth-Imaging System (REIS). The constellation offered high-resolution optical images (5m) with a daily global coverage. (<https://earth.esa.int/>)

QuickBird-2: This was an Earth-imaging satellite owned by Maxar, operational between October 2001 and 2015. QuickBird generated high-resolution imagery at 1 and 1,5m with a revisit time of 2.8 and 1.5, respectively. Data were used to analyse changes in land use, forest, agriculture and climate. (<https://earth.esa.int/>).

3. 4 EUMETSAT Meteorology Missions

MSG: the Meteosat Second Generation is a joint project between ESA and EUMETSAT.

MetOp: It is Europe's first polar-orbiting satellite dedicated to operational meteorology. MetOp is a series of three satellites launched sequentially over 12 years from October 2006 to November 2018. The series provides data for both operational meteorology and climate studies.

3.5 Other Missions:

SPOT VGT

French SPOT: SPOT (Satellite Pour l'Observation de la Terre) consists of a series of earth observation satellites providing high-resolution images of the Earth. SPOT-4 and SPOT-5 include sensors called VEGETATION able to monitor continental ecosystems.

OSTM/Jason-2: (2008-2019): the OSTM/JASON-2 French-American satellite provided precise measurements of ocean surface topography, surface wind speed, and wave height; as this type of measurement is a crucial requirement for the Copernicus Marine Services, the European Commission has included this type of mission in its latest communication on the future Copernicus Space Component as Sentinel-6.

SWOT: Surface Water and Ocean Topography is a product of a joint collaboration between NASA, CNES, CSA and UKSA, launched on December 2022. SWOT is a swath-base SAR altimetry mission continuing from Jason-1, -2, and -3 missions. SWOT is the first satellite mission that will observe nearly all water on Earth's surface, measuring the height of water in the planet's lakes, rivers, reservoirs, and the ocean (<https://swot.jpl.nasa.gov/>).

Figure 7.- The ESA-developed Earth Observation Missions; some additional missions are being proposed beyond 2025 in the Science and Copernicus Programmes. Credit: ESA

4- Identified needs for water quantity

During the project development, several work packages have been collecting user requirements for water quality, quantity, in-situ and modelling. To complement the user requirements collection and get specific information on the sensors and missions used by the users, a brief questionnaire was distributed from Task 3.5 to all members of the H2020 Water-ForCE inland water quantity and modelling Working Group. The survey was distributed between December 2022-January 2023 and was designed to collect the actual and potential use of Copernicus remote sensing component and to obtain a user evaluation of the Copernicus remote sensing products and services. The results of the survey are commented in Section 4.1, while Section 4.2 summarizes the demands specifically related to the sensors or missions' characteristics for water quantity monitoring coming from previous deliverables in the project (Section 4.1).

4.1 Results of the Working Group survey

To identify and collect the requirements from the users' point of view, a questionnaire was created and distributed among the members of the Water-ForCE Water Quantity Working Group during December 2022-January 2023. The questions included can be seen on <https://forms.office.com/e/WwZxje4mqk> and are also attached to this document as an Annex 1, as well as the responses (Annex 2). In this section we summarize the answers get for every question.

1. Which are the usual topics of your activities in the water domain?

Hydrological and hydrodynamic modelling are the more frequent, but also groundwater and soil moisture monitoring, flood forecasting and flood risk/hazard assessment were mentioned.

2. Could you list the main remote sensing products or services that you use?

The list of used remote sensing products and services is very broad, including Copernicus and non Copernicus products, but can be summarized into few categories:

- Copernicus Water Level (Hydroweb)
- GRACE gravimetry
- Altimetry
- Sentinel 1, 2, 3, 6 raw data
- Soil moisture products (CCI)
- Water storage (Copernicus)
- Water extent (S1, S2)
- Snow & ice products (S1, S2)
- Landsat
- Other products

. The following table lists the mentioned ones:

Main remote sensing products or services used			
Product/Service	Copernicus	Product/Service	Copernicus

Hydroweb (Copernicus Global Land Water Level)	Yes	CCI Soil Moisture Products	Yes
Sentinel-2 L1C	Yes	Copernicus services on water storage variables	Yes
Sentinel-1 L1C	Yes	Nadir altimetry (from any available mission)	Yes
Sentinel-3 SRAL L1b	Yes	Combined radar-optic images	Yes
Sentinel-6 L1b	Yes	Global River Width from Landsat (GRWL)	No
Sentinel Playground	Yes	MERIT	No
Earth Observation Browser	Yes	Hydrosheds	No
Google Earth Engine	No	Water extent from S-1, S-2	Yes
Landsat	No	Snow and Ice products from S-1 & S-2	Yes
MODIS	Yes	IOSIN EMSO-EUXINUS (Romanian coastal stations)	No
Satellite gravimetry (GRACE, GRACE-FO)	No		
Future products and services			
Sentinel-derived products in hydroweb.next		SWOT	

Table 1.- Main remote sensing products or services mentioned in the Working Group survey.

3.From those, which ones are not from Copernicus?

Also, the list of non-Copernicus used products is very variable, as can be seen in Table 2.

Non Copernicus products or services used	
Product/Service	Product/Service
hydroweb.next (French Hydrology Thematic Hub)	Jason
SWOT	Envisat
Google Earth Engine	DAHITI
Landsat	ICESat

MODIS	Some of them could come from CNES/theia platform (water level) but they are the same products than Copernicus (hydroweb).
Terrestrial gravimetry and groundwater from satellite gravimetry (GRACE and GRACE-FO)	IOSIN EMSO-EUXINUS (Romanian coastal stations)
MERIT	

Table 2.- Non-Copernicus products or services mentioned in the Working Group survey.

4. What is your non-Copernicus products selection/decision based on?

The lack of knowledge of the existence or not of suitable Copernicus products is the main reason for not using the Copernicus products/services (43%). In other cases, preference for the external products over the Copernicus ones (29%) or no available products in Copernicus are the reasons (28%).

Figure 8.- Responses to question 4 of the Working Group survey.

When asked to explain why they prefer the non-Copernicus products to the Copernicus ones, the only received answer is:

Sentinel-derived products in hydroweb.next will reach the full space resolution of Sentinel-2/Sentinel-1 (10-20m) for water detection and water quality. We need these resolutions to validate SWOT data

7. Do you use Sentinel products?

57% of the respondents are using Sentinel products. Among the rest, 29% don't use them directly, and another 14% have the intention to use them.

Figure 9.- Responses to question 7 of the Working Group survey.

8. Could you list the main ones that you use?

Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-3 are the most used, followed by Sentinel-6 data and Copernicus Global Land products.

Figure 10.- Responses to question 8 of the Working Group survey.

9. Which improved features (spatial, time or radiometric resolution, spectral bands configuration ...) of these existing products could improve your water related activities?

Spatial resolution is the most mentioned, but also temporal acquisition is important.

Figure 11.- Responses to question 9 of the Working Group survey.

10. Which current features are further away from your needs?

Most users didn't know it, but one clear answer was radiometric.

Figure 12.- Responses to question 10 of the Working Group survey.

11. Are you aware about the future Sentinel missions?

67% of the respondents were aware of the future Sentinel missions, while 33% were not.

Figure 13.- Responses to question 11 of the Working Group survey.

12. In case you know them, do you think they will solve/improve some current problems/barriers of your work? Please include a short explanation.

All the respondents agreed that the future missions will contribute to improve their work. These are the main benefits they mentioned:

- Concerning water level and altimetry, we lack a Copernicus mission that will provide more than nadir information like SWOT. It should be part of Sentinel-3-NG programm.
- We should be able to monitor water level and extent consistently for as many water bodies as possible, with the best time resolution as possible

- CHIME maybe will give a better land-cover mapping complementing Sentinel-2 data
- Rivers with small - medium width (e.g. 10 - 50 m wide) observation is needed for a better flood and climate change risk assessment/mitigation and future urban planning.
- Waiting from hyperspectral missions and S3NG constellation to improve hydrologic parameter monitoring
- Yes, they could improve the modelling results and they could be used for calibration.

13. In case you know them, will they allow you to carry on new activities? Please include a short explanation.

Most of the respondents considered that new Sentinel missions will allow them to carry on new activities.

These are the comments they mentioned:

- Better flood and climate change risk assessment/mitigation and future urban planning.
- Defining better forcing and boundary conditions, as well as for model calibration.

14. Do you have some additional suggestions for the new remote sensing products/services based on future Sentinels?

Several responses were collected:

- Having a thematic hub dedicated to hydrology gathering all interesting data with adhoc features for hydrology users would be of great help
- Mass change missions (satellite gravimetry)
- Data from remote sensing could be downloaded or converted to text files to be used in a model that can read from text files.

As a summary of the survey conclusions, we can say that:

- Sentinel 1 and 2 raw data and derived products (water level, water storage) are the most used.
- There is not a highly used clear product outside Copernicus, except for gravimetry (GRACE and GRACE-FO) and nadir altimetry.

- It seems that lack of knowledge is the main reason for who does not use Copernicus products. The second reason is the preference for an alternative product outside Copernicus, and only in few cases, a Copernicus product doesn't exist.
- Sentinel products are widely accepted in general, since they are quite used and users show intentions to use them.
- Clearly, Sentinels 1-2-3 are the most used.
- Spatial resolution is the most mentioned feature for improving water related activities, but also temporal acquisition is important.
- Only radiometric resolution is mentioned as being further away from users' needs.
- In general, users are aware of the future Sentinel missions.
- Future Sentinel missions are expected to improve land-cover mapping and hydrologic parameter monitoring and modelling.
- They will allow to carry on better flood and climate change risk assessment/mitigation and future urban planning and can help in models calibration.
- Demands for new remote sensing products/services based on future Sentinels are:
 - Mass change missions (satellite gravimetry)
 - A Copernicus mission that will provide more than nadir information like SWOT
 - The ability to observe rivers with small - medium width (e.g. 10 - 50 m wide).
- Derived proposals from the survey include:
 - Better promotion and communication of the existing and available products and services in Copernicus in order to reach potential users.
 - Having a thematic hub dedicated to hydrology gathering all interesting data with adhoc features for hydrology users.
 - Data from remote sensing could be downloaded or converted to text files to be used in a model that can read from text files.

4.2 Other identified user requirements

During the several workshops and meetings conducted within the project with the expert groups, user requirements have been obtained concerning the use of Copernicus products and services in water studies. The full collection of user demands have been summarized in previous deliverables, that we analyse here to extract the needs in terms of better performance of Copernicus satellites and missions for the provision of water quantity information.

- No detailed regional products (only global products) are available in Copernicus for **Water levels in lakes and rivers**. This can difficult the high resolution modelling in detailed or regional hydrodynamic, river or water balance models. On the contrary, Digital Elevation Model (DEM) information is available only for the EEA39 region and groundwater recharge data only for greater Europe, so not useful for global studies.
 - [CLMS Water level](#). Sensor: Altimeters
 - [C3S Water level](#). Sensor: radar altimeters
- **Surface water** variables (such as surface runoff and river discharge or flood extent) would work better with a higher spatial resolution for predicting extent of floods (<1 km). But in general, good temporal resolutions are provided in Copernicus for hydrodynamic modelling.
- An **evapotranspiration** product is missing for assessing water use efficiency, monitoring rates of irrigation water use, monitoring river flows, monitoring and forecasting drought or conducting integrated assessment of water availability under climate change scenarios. This is a great issue highly demanded by users and they demand in finest spatial resolution as possible (Guzinska et al 2019). Evapotranspiration estimates are key variables regarding the use of water in agriculture for the production of indicators required by the Common Agricultural Policy. According to 2019 Copernicus user consultation there is a need from the community for seasonal maps based on daily to weekly information and a 5-20 m pixel resolution to go for 1 ha minimum mapping unit.
- When assessing river flows and monitoring and forecasting drought, **snow and ice extent** or **groundwater** availability are useful variables. Snowmelt products in

Copernicus are offered at >1000 m spatial resolution, while finer resolutions would be appropriate (10-1000 m), Groundwater recharge is available in annual, seasonal or monthly values, while hourly or daily frequencies would be desirable. In general, there is a high demand and limited availability of data products for groundwater.

- Snowmelt. Source: ERA 5 (Modelled).
- Snow water equivalent. Source: Snow water equivalent (mm) derived from satellite measurements (AMSR-E microwave radiometer on EOS-Aqua) with assimilated ground observations for the specified date.
- Snow water equivalent. Source: LISFLOOD simulated amount of snow (mm water equivalent) for the specified date based on observed meteorological input.
- Snow thickness. Source: based on the hourly ECMWF ERA5 data at surface level and is referred to as AgERA5.
- [Groundwater recharge](#). Source: modelled
- A **bathymetry** product is required for water modelling. It seems that there are plans to derive Copernicus satellite derived bathymetry product in the Marine Service. For the moment, EMODNET bathymetry, developed jointly by EMODNET and the Marine Service, is being used.
- For **soil moisture** products, there is a demand from various user communities for higher spatial resolution datasets at kilometre scale (Peng et al 2021). The current and future missions provide opportunities to develop high spatial resolution soil moisture products and with moderate (e.g., daily) temporal resolution. In general, there is a high demand and limited availability of data products for soil properties.
 - [Soil moisture](#). Source: a large set of satellite sensors
 - [Soil moisture](#). Source: Relative soil moisture for soil depths 0.1m (red) to 1m (blue) for the specified date as derived from the advanced scatterometer (ASCAT) on board the METOP satellite. Relative soil moisture is calculated using a weighted average of the three different soil moisture layers provided by ASCAT.
- **Increased resolution** (sub 1m) is needed in order to identify smaller inland water bodies and provide information on hydromorphology of rivers. There is a focus on marine environments and big lakes (neglecting rivers and floodplains)

- For urban water management, river basin management, and hazards/emergency management, there is a lack of radar exploitation. The **integration** of radar data and services and the integration of spectroradiometers in the existing infrastructures, as well as the wider collection of hyperspectral radiometry are demands from these sectors. A spatial resolution of 1-5 m is also desirable.
- **Time resolution** yearly and seasonal maps based on daily to weekly information are required in agriculture, as well as spatial resolutions of 5-20 m pixel to go for 1 ha minimum mapping unit.
- In general, **higher spatial resolutions** and **long term time series** are needed. In particular, high resolution and change over time is required for studying the geomorphology of rivers and estuaries, to detect change in land cover over time and water availability trends, identify the type of water body, water level and if permanent or temporary water body and to monitor illegal activities, sedimentation and flood hazards. Increasing product resolutions remains top priority.
- There are also some demands related to **lack of data**:
 - Coastal information
 - Basin-scale high resolution surface models and topography data
 - Near “real-time” forecasts to improve early warning systems, for example flood alerts.
 - Data on man-made structures (dams,..).

6.- Copernicus next future improvements

During the workshops and meetings conducted within the project, updates on the new foreseen improvements and developments by the different Services have been collected, some of them related to existing or new Copernicus sensors and missions. In this Section, we summarize the relevant planned improvements by the Services.

The Global Land Service offers several products and data related to water quantity. The improvements it is planning to implement in the future are:

- Snow water equivalent (derived from Passive MW radiometer (SSM/I/S) + Synop SD obs.): reduce the spatial resolution from 5 km to 1 km
- Snow Cover Extent (Northern Hemisphere 1km, derived from Suomi-NPP VIIRS data): Transitioning to Sentinel-3 SLSTR data
- Snow Cover Extent (European 500 m, derived from MODIS): Use of Sentinel-3A/B SLSTR data
- Lake Ice Extent (derived from MODIS data): 500m Global product with S3-SLSTR data + exploiting Sentinel-3 SLSTR/OLCI L1C synergy data
- Surface Soil Moisture (derived from Sentinel-1 C-band SAR): no plans
- Soil Water Index (1 km, derived from Sentinel-1 C-band SAR + Metop ASCAT): no plans
- Soil Water Index (0.1°, derived from Metop ASCAT): no plans
- Water Bodies extent (100m and 300m monthly products based on S2 data): Connection with Surfwater project (CNES): S2 as well as S1 SAR data
- Lakes and Rivers Water Level (derived from Jason 2&3, Sentinel-3A&B data SRAL): Addition of Sentinel-6A: ensure the continuation of measurements on the Jason ground track. S6 uses SAR mode (similarly to S3A&B): improved accuracy expected w.r.t J3. Continue expanding the number of virtual stations and lakes: Given the OLTC updates for Jason-3, Sentinel-3A and Sentinel-3B that were performed in 2020 about 3000 new products are expected. Addition of Sentinel-3C

The Copernicus Emergency Management Service develops the Global automatic satellite-based flood monitoring (GFM), providing a large set of variables derived from Sentinel-1 SAR. It is planning to further increase the revisit frequency with Sentinel-1 C.

Some of the foreseen improvements in Copernicus services and products in relation to water quantity have been released during the 2021-2022 period. This is the case of the new High-Resolution Ocean Colour (HR OC) Products for the Coastal stripes of 20km for all European Seas, launched on May 5th 2021 and which can be accessed via the CMEMS portal (https://resources.marine.copernicus.eu/?option=com_csw&task=results). As already mentioned in Water-ForCE deliverable D3.2, further improvements could include merging Sentinel 3 derived products with the newly developed Sentinel 2 products, and the

production of global HR-OC products, since they are now only available for the European seas.

The Copernicus Climate Change Service was planning to launch 2 new products by the end of 2022, Ice Surface Temperature and Sea Ice Drift, and is planning to launch 3 new products in the future, among them a Micro-wave based precipitation product. Also, the priorities for the evolution of the Service are focused on the Cryosphere (Snow & Permafrost) and Hydrosphere (River discharge) (Muñoz Sabater, 2022).

The Copernicus Land Monitoring Service started to provide Near Real Time (NRT) geospatial information with the launch of the High Resolution Snow and Ice service (HR-S&I) providing snow & ice products, which are already included in our analysis. It also plans to provide some new bio-geophysical variables (e.g. evapotranspiration, global phenology,...) and products for sectoral support (like Irrigation and others to support SDG 6.6.1 and SDG 15.3).

CIMR will provide a large number of Level-2 geophysical products to be derived over all earth surfaces including sea ice (concentration, thickness, drift, ice type, ice surface temperature), sea surface temperature, sea surface salinity, wind vector over the ocean surface, snow parameters, soil moisture, land surface temperature, vegetation indices, and atmospheric water parameters serving all of the Copernicus Services.

The primary objectives of **CRISTAL** target mainly cryosphere science: measuring and monitoring variability of sea ice thickness and its snow depth, and measuring and monitoring the surface elevation and changes of polar glaciers and ice sheets. CRISTAL will also support applications related to snow cover and permafrost in Arctic regions. In addition to those objectives CRISTAL is expected to contribute significantly to oceanography, like CryoSat-2.

Although Sentinel-3 routinely delivers global LST measurements, its limited 1 km spatial resolution does not capture the field-scale variability required for irrigation management, crop growth modelling and reporting on crop water productivity. The Expansion Mission **LSTM** will enable monitoring evapotranspiration rate at European field scale by capturing

the variability of LST (and hence ET) allowing more robust estimates of field scale water productivity. It will provide systematic global acquisitions of high-resolution (50 meters) observations with a high revisit frequency (1-3 days).

ROSE-L will provide Sea ice type, sea ice concentration, sea ice motion, glacier/ice cap surface velocity, grounding line and snow water equivalent (SWE) in support of Cryosphere and Arctic application needs, soil moisture at regional and global scale to support improved weather forecasts, hydrology and water management, as well as other forest related variables.

To increase spatial and temporal coverage of Sentinel 2, on-demand pilot products include Level-2H (harmonised Sentinel-2 + Landsat 8/9 surface reflectances) and Level-2F (fused Sentinel-2 + Landsat 8/9 surface reflectances).

Sentinel 2 data is being reprocessed with global refinement and Copernicus DEM (90 m) since January 2022. Reprocessing duration 9 months.

7.- Discussion

The demand for the **increase of the temporal and spatial resolution** is one of the repeated suggestions for many sorts of users, and for a variety of applications (predicting extent of floods, assessing river flows, monitoring and forecasting drought, agriculture, hazards/emergencies). A high spatial resolution is crucial to identify smaller inland water bodies and provide information on hydromorphology of rivers. This demand has been collected in nearly all the workshops and questionnaires performed in the project, as shown in the previous sections, and it seems that it will never end. Sentinels NG are planned to advance in the **spatial and temporal resolution improvement**, Particularly, on the improvement on the revisit frequency of Sentinel NG, the recommended option for optical sensors is to increase the number of satellites instead of the increase of the field of view, because the non-desired impact of directional effects on the variability and uncertainty of the reflectance values. The increase of the number of satellites provide another very

interesting characteristic, the redundancy mitigates potential technical problems on the Sentinels platforms and sensors, as the current Sentinel 1.

Meanwhile Sentinels NG arrives and for the ongoing studies and applications which need historical data, some solutions could partially address to the higher spatial demands:

- To open repositories of the contributing missions:
Despite their limitations (short time series, low number of bands, sometimes only VIS, uncompleted global coverage, etc.), free access to the contributing missions' image repository and derived products could provide valuable data to some applications.
- To Open catalogues / repositories of UAV Images
Their limitations are much higher than contributing missions, but specially for local studies, the very high spatial resolution information by UAVs could be very useful. The catalogue would be the best way to discover potential UAV Images at specific regions of interest. The second step would be to build repositories.

The increase of temporal resolution is essential for monitoring rapid changes and flash phenomena, but it is also needed in other applications as indicated by the users such as in agriculture, water extent monitoring and specially to increase the probabilities of obtaining valid images in often cloud cover regions in any type of water quantity monitoring studies.

The main solutions lay in the multi-sensor approach:

- Gap filling
A complementary source of images is used for filling specific and short missing periods of the main type of Images. The complementary source characteristics are adapted to the main one by simple replacing methods (resampling, nearest radiometric band, etc..) or more complex (machine learning, Sarafanov et al 2020)
- Virtual constellation
This method builds a synthetic dataset coming from different satellite missions with similar characteristics (Wulder et al. 2015). The synthesis product is generated globally for the times series in a harmonized dataset like the images would be captured from the satellites (Claverie et al. 2018). It is not addressed to specific gaps in regions or time periods. Sometimes, the product has the best properties of their components or generated with intermediate values.

The future Sentinels missions, next generation and expansion, will provide more detailed information on different dimensions: spectral, spatial and temporal. This means that we will be able to avoid part of these merging solutions, however we will always find that for specific applications we will need more and more detail, and again the multi-sensor approach solutions will help. Some demands from the users go in that direction (waiting from hyperspectral missions and S3NG constellation to improve hydrologic parameter monitoring, CHIME complementing Sentinel 2, integration of spectroradiometers in the existing infrastructures, integration of radar data and services).

Many studies on water quantity dynamics, for instance related to the impact of climate change on water resources availability, need **long time series** (Li et al 2022). In this case, the time resolution is not so relevant, the key characteristic is the coherence of the long time series, therefore the discontinuity of missions is a big barrier. As an example, the end of MERIS has partially been solved with OLCI Sentinel-3, however there is a gap that can be filled in some cases (Defourny et al. 2016 by PROBA-V), again, the archive from the contributing missions is very useful. The paradigm of success continuity mission is Landsat; in 2022 it achieved 50 years (Wulder et al. 2022). Thus, for the future missions the **continuity** of the current missions must be a top priority, and very Important, the new sensors can extend some features (more bands for some applications, not needed in all satellites of the constellation (Inglada, et al 2022), but the existing ones must be preserved, we need consistent time series.

In relation to the **radiometry** dimension, the current Sentinels cover a wide range of spectral bands, but not in all spectral regions. Indeed, this has been the only common current feature indicated as further away from the needs of the users in the questionnaire distributed in Task 3.5. The TIR (thermal infrared) is only provided at medium resolution, Sentinel-3, however it is missing in Sentinel-2. One of the main variables used in the monitoring of water stress in agriculture, forestry and drought indices for Copernicus EDO (<https://edo.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>) is the **evapotranspiration** which needs thermal information. Specially for the agriculture, the high spatial resolution is a key feature. The planned LSTM will be very welcome in those sectors, meanwhile different merging solutions cover this gap: Guzinski and Nieto 2019, ESA SEN4ET project (<https://www.esa-sen4et.org/> project) or the use ET products by Landsat TIRS (Senay et al. 2016).

The coming contribution of the hyperspectral mission CHIME is very relevant for water quality applications, less important for water quantity ones, however hyperspectral RS is used for some indirect indicators in vegetation, e.g. foliage water content (Watt et al. 2021).

Inland water products from Copernicus are relatively new. They include inland water, wetness, snow and land ice products. Water levels are computed for lakes larger than 50 ha and intersections of major river networks. At pan-European level, Copernicus produces water and wetness products (permanent water, temporary water, permanent wetness and temporary wetness), a water and wetness probability index and water bodies' areas covered by inland water along the year. Copernicus at this stage does not provide regular information on **rivers dynamics** and especially on river runoff and overall hydrological dynamics, nor on under water systems. S3NG-TC should help to leverage substantially this gap within the Copernicus services. The S3NG-T mission shall provide Level-2 Water Surface Elevation for all targets within the Hydrology Target Mask with a total standard uncertainty of ≤ 24 cm with an enhanced goal: ≤ 10 cm. The **S3NG-T** baseline continuity mission shall provide Level-2 river discharge estimates for medium to large rivers with a width of ≥ 3 km within the Hydrology Target Mask with a total standard uncertainty of $\leq 20\%$. **ROSE-L** will allow high-resolution monitoring of soil moisture below the vegetation canopy over most vegetated land cover types and throughout the growing season and enhanced monitoring of the Arctic and Cryosphere through improved sea ice mapping, iceberg detection, extending the monitoring of glaciers and ice caps and addressing the information gaps in Snow Water Content (SWE).

L-band measurements from SMOS, SMAP and Aquarius have been a huge success serving a multitude of applications related to the water cycle. Since the SMOS launch, several variables related to the cryosphere have been studied: sea ice thickness, frozen soil, continental ice sheets temperature, and snow liquid water content. L-band allows monitoring of **thin sea ice** (< 1 m). Thinner sea ice dominates the heat exchange between the ocean and the atmosphere in the central Arctic and it is an essential climate parameter to understand the Arctic amplification (warming in the Arctic has been much faster than the rest of the world). **Soil moisture information** has been used for drought monitoring, precipitation estimations and agricultural purposes including yield prediction.

It is acknowledged that the CIMR mission will provide continuity of L-band measurements albeit at a coarser spatial resolution and without the multi-angular viewing capability that is essential to separate the different contributors to the signals (e.g. from the vegetation and the underlying soil). In addition, the key requirement for a follow-on mission, i.e. an increased spatial resolution of 10 – 15 km, cannot be met with the technology selected for CIMR.

Finally, the water storages measurements in groundwater reservoirs are essential in many regions for understanding the complete water cycle. Groundwater availability is also a recurrent demand in many user requirements studies. Groundwater studies need the continuity of the **gravimetry missions** (Bonsor et al 2010) ESA GOCE and NASA/DLR GRACE and GRACE-FO. The water quantity community needs an Impulse of the NGGM (Next Generation of Gravity Missions), Haagmans et al 2020.

8.- Conclusions for new Sentinel missions on water quantity

The cross analysis of the user requirements collected by several Water-ForCE user consultation activities plus the reviewed bibliography with the Sentinels current and next future properties provides these summarized conclusions:

- The planned **increase of spatial and temporal resolutions** of Sentinels NG totally agrees with the most sources of user requirements analysed in this document.
- The addition of specific spectral bands in existing multispectral sensors or the move to hyperspectral is not an important demand for the water quantity users (attention, it is very relevant for water quality purposes). There is an exception, water quantity users demand a high spatial resolution thermal band for the models and studies in which **evapotranspiration** is a key variable.
- The optical missions formed by pairs (A/B or C/D) of satellites or even more, multiple satellites, is the recommended solution for the demands on the increasing of the

time resolution, moreover it offers a mitigation measure for the risks of technical permanent problems.

- Next Sentinels missions in any potential re-design of spectral band configuration, can add more specific bands, however without any replacement, they should preserve the existing ones. The **continuity** between missions, with inter-band consistency and sensor intercalibration, is crucial for the long time series studies.
- Sentinel-3NG-T+ ROSE-L will fill the current gap of information in **river dynamics**, monitoring of glaciers and ice caps.
- **Soil moisture information** from ESA Earth Explorers missions as SMOS are useful for drought monitoring, precipitation estimations and agricultural purposes and their continuity is recommended.
- **Gravimetric** missions are needed to monitor the groundwater resources and understand the transfer process between surface and ground levels.

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Annex 1

Working Group survey questions

Water-ForCE - Copernicus Remote Sensing

Thank you for participating in this survey which is sent to all members of the H2020 Water-ForCE inland water quantity and modelling Working Group. If you have received this survey from a colleague and you are not a member of the Working Group, you are still welcome to complete the survey! At the end of the survey you can indicate to be kept informed of any results and can become a member of the Working Group.

Some questions may not be relevant to your expertise. Please feel free to answer as many questions as you see fit - any question can be skipped. Some questions come with a free comment field through which you can share suggestions.

Please provide your response as soon as possible, ideally by Dec 15th, to allow time for aggregation and final analysis.

1. Which are the usual topics of your activities in the water domain?

2. Could you list the main remote sensing products or services that you use?

3. From those, which ones are not from Copernicus?

4. What is your non-Copernicus products selection/decision based on?

- There is not a similar product in Copernicus
- There is a similar product in Copernicus, however I prefer the mentioned one
- I don't know if there is or not a similar product in Copernicus, this product is useful for my work
- Other

5. Please explain why

6. Please indicate which

7. Do you use Sentinel products?

8. Could you list the main ones that you use?

9. Which improved features (spatial, time or radiometric resolution, spectral bands configuration, ...) of these existing products could improve your water related activities? Please try to prioritize them.

10. Which current features are further away from your needs?

11. Are you aware about the future Sentinel missions?

(See more information at:

https://www.esa.int/Applications/Observing_the_Earth/Copernicus/The_Sentinel_missions and

https://www.esa.int/Applications/Observing_the_Earth/Copernicus/Copernicus_Sentinel_Expansion_missions)

12. In case you know them, do you think they will solve/improve some current problems/barriers of your work? Please include a short explanation.

13. In case you know them, will they allow you to carry on new activities? Please include a short explanation.

14. Do you have some additional suggestions for the new remote sensing products/services based on future Sentinels?

15. Thank you for filling the survey. We really appreciate you inputs and your time, which will contribute to define better products and services in Copernicus for water research and management.

If you want to become a member of the Water-ForCE Inland Water quantity/Modelling Working Group, please visit <https://waterforce.eu/contact>

Este contenido no está creado ni respaldado por Microsoft. Los datos que envíe se enviarán al propietario del formulario.

Annex 2

Working Group survey responses

1. Which are the usual topics of your activities in the water domain?

development, operation and validation of remote sensing products dedicated to hydrology

Flood risk/hazard assessment ;

Critical Infrastructure Protection

Quantifying the water cycle, in particular assessing water storage and soil moisture variations from local to global scales

river modeling, hydrodynamic modeling, flood forecasting, observing rivers from space

hydrological modelling and forecasting through assimilation of water level , water extent

Water quality monitoring

Snow and Ice monitoring

Numerical modelling of water dynamics in coastal zone and in surface water

Groundwater monitoring and assessment

2. Could you list the main remote sensing products or services that you use?

Hydroweb (Copernicus Global Land Water Level), Copernicus Global Land LSWT, Copernicus Global Land LWQ, Sentinel-2 L1C, Sentinel-1 L1C, Sentinel-3 SRAL L1b, Sentinel-6 L1b. Soon: Sentinel-derived products in hydroweb.next, SWOT

Services > Sentinel Playground; Earth Observation Browser; Google Earth Engine; QGIS (plug-ins) for

- Satellite imagery interpretation and classification;
- Classification-supervised and unsupervised;
- Change detection;
- Land cover classification;
- Water mapping; etc.

Products > Sentinel 2 ; Landsat ; MODIS

Satellite gravimetry (GRACE, GRACE-FO) for groundwater and terrestrial water storage

CCI Soil Moisture Products
Copernicus services on water storage variables
nadir altimetry (from any available mission), combined radar-optic images, DEM
GRWL, MERIT, Hydrosheds
Water level from altimetry
water extent from S-1, S-2
All products could come from the land and emergency services for operational activities
water quality L1 products from S-2
Snow and Ice products from S-1 & S-2
IOSIN EMSO-EUXINUS (Romanian coastal stations)
Navionics
GRACE, GRACE-FO, and the network of Copernicus satellites

3. From those, which ones are not from Copernicus?

hydroweb.next (French Hydrology Thematic Hub), SWOT
Services > Google Earth Engine; QGIS
Products > Landsat ; MODIS
Terrestrial gravimetry and groundwater from satellite gravimetry
MERIT, Jason, Envisat, DAHITI, ICESat, soon SWOT
some of them could come from CNES/theia platform (water level) but they are the same products than Copernicus (hydroweb).
IOSIN EMSO-EUXINUS (Romanian coastal stations)
Navionics
GRACE and GRACE-FO

4. What is your non-Copernicus products selection/decision based on?

There is a similar product in Copernicus, however I prefer the mentioned one

I don't know if there is or not a similar product in Copernicus, this product is useful for my work
There is not a similar product in Copernicus
I don't know if there is or not a similar product in Copernicus, this product is useful for my work
There is a similar product in Copernicus, however I prefer the mentioned one
I don't know if there is or not a similar product in Copernicus, this product is useful for my work
There is not a similar product in Copernicus

5. Please explain why

Sentinel-derived products in hydroweb.next will reach the full space resolution of Sentinel-2/Sentinel-1 (10-20m) for water detection and water quality. We need these resolutions to validate SWOT data

6. Please indicate which

7. Do you use Sentinel products?

yes
Yes, 99%
not directly by myself
Yes
yes
Not yet, but I intend to.
I am not sure because I don't work directly with the satellite data myself, but I am involved in projects where they are used.

8. Could you list the main ones that you use?

Hydroweb (Copernicus Global Land Water Level), Copernicus Global Land LSWT,
 Copernicus Global Land LWQ, Sentinel-2 L1C, Sentinel-1 L1C, Sentinel-3 SRAL L1b, Sentinel-
 6 L1b
 Sentinel 2 - 99%
 Sentinel 1 - 1%
 S1, S2, S3, soon S6
 S-1 for Wet snow
 S-2 for water quality, snow & Ice
 S-3 for water level
 No

9. Which improved features (spatial, time or radiometric resolution, spectral bands configuration ...) of these existing products could improve your water related activities?

time, spatial (resolution and coverage), radiometric
 Resolution;
 Temporal acquisition;
 mass change data with higher spatial resolution to assess groundwater, soil moisture and terrestrial water storage changes
 anything that can give additionnal information
 spatial resolution (20m) from S-2 for water quality and snow&lce monitoring
 I cannot answer, as I haven't used them yet.

10. Which current features are further away from your needs?

radiometric
 I don't know, there are a lot of them that I do not use (e.g. spectral bands, Indices)
 I cannot answer, as I haven't used them yet.

11. Are you aware about the future Sentinel missions?

yes

Yes
some basics, yes
no
yes
Not really

12. In case you know them, do you think they will solve/improve some current problems/barriers of your work? Please include a short explanation.

no concerning land/water masks, my concerns are more related to the information we can extract from the current missions.
Concerning water level and altimetry, we lack a copernicus mission that will provide more than nadir information like SWOT. It should be part of Sentinel-3-NG programm but should be stresses here: we should be able to monitor water level and extent consistently for as many water bodies as possible, with the best time resolution as possible
CHIME maybe will give a better land-cover mapping complementing Sentinel-2 data, but I don't know if that will resolve the problem of resolution.
Rivers with small - medium width (e.g. 10 - 50 m wide) observation is needed for a better flood and climate change risk assessment/mitigation and future urban planning.
We are mainly waiting from hyperspectral missions and S3NG constellation to improve hydrologic parameter monitoring
Yes, I am sure that they could improve the modelling results and they could be used for calibration.

13. In case you know them, will they allow you to carry on new activities? Please include a short explanation.

Rivers with small - medium width (e.g. 10 - 50 m wide) observation is needed for a better flood and climate change risk assessment/mitigation and future urban planning.
not directly for now in my field of research
yes see above
Yes, of course. I am sure that such data could be used in defining better forcing and boundary conditions, as well as for model calibration.

14. Do you have some additional suggestions for the new remote sensing products/services based on future Sentinels?

the access to hydrology data is spread accross many Copernicus Services and other platforms. Having a thematic hub dedicated to hydrology gathering all interesting data with adhoc features for hydrology users would be of great help

Not for now.

mass change missions (satellite gravimetry)

I am not really entitled to have an opinion. But I think it would help if data from remote sensing could be downloaded or converted to text files. I use a model that can read from text files.